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Cost-effectiveness of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention among preschool children with severe anaemia in Malawi, Kenya, and Uganda

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Cost-effectiveness of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention among preschool children with severe anaemia in Malawi, Kenya, and Uganda

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Children hospitalised with severe anaemia in malaria-endemic areas are at high risk of dying or being re-admitted during the first six months after discharge. Previous trials in Malawi, Kenya, and Uganda showed that three months of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC) with monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) substantially reduces this risk. We aimed to conduct a cost-effectiveness analysis of community-based PMC (dispensing all three DP courses to caregivers at discharge from hospital), facility-based PMC (monthly dispensing of PMC-DP courses at the hospital), compared to the standard of care (artemether-lumefantrine at discharge), which provides two weeks of post-treatment prophylaxis.

Method: Three Markov decision models, one each for Malawi, Kenya, and Uganda, were used to compare the strategies' relative cost-effectiveness, reporting results in incremental cost-effectiveness ratios. Deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analyses were conducted for each country to account for uncertainty. The efficacy data were obtained from a placebo-controlled trial in Kenya and Uganda (n=1049). Adherence data stemmed from an implementation trial in Malawi (n=375).

Findings: In all three countries, both PMC strategies were cost-saving as they were less costly and more effective in terms of increased health-adjusted life expectancy than the standard of care from a societal perspective in the three countries. Community-based PMC was less costly and more effective than both the facility-based PMC and the standard of care. These results remained robust in the deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analyses.

Interpretation: Monthly PMC under implementation conditions in malaria-endemic areas is cost-saving, particularly when caretakers are provided all three courses at discharge to the caregivers to administer at home.

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INTRODUCTION

Despite large-scale control efforts, malaria burden reductions have stagnated in parts of sub-Saharan Africa. Severe anaemia remains a leading cause of mortality and morbidity in children under five years of age, and malaria is one of the main causes.¹⁻⁵ In highly malaria-endemic areas, severe anaemia may be found in approximately one-third of hospitalised children and contribute to 50% of deaths attributed to malaria.

Young children discharged from hospital after treatment for severe anaemia are at high risk of readmission at least six months post-discharge.^{1,5-7} A meta-analysis found their odds of death during this period 72% higher than during hospitalisation. A multi-country trial in Kenya and Uganda showed that in preschool children with severe anaemia, three months of monthly post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC) with the long-acting antimalarial dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) substantially reduced the risk of malaria-associated readmission or death in the first three months after hospital discharge.⁷

A trial in Malawi compared community-based versus facility-based delivery strategies for PMC to assess adherence to all three courses of PMC under implementation conditions.⁸ The highest adherence was achieved with community-based delivery where caregivers were provided with all three courses at discharge with instructions to administer PMC monthly at home. Caregiver adherence to all three courses influences the effectiveness and, thus, the cost-effectiveness of PMC. We combined data from both trials to establish the cost-effectiveness of PMC under programmatic conditions and inform national and international guideline development for PMC in malaria-endemic areas in Africa.

METHOD

DATA SOURCES

Data from both these recently completed clinical trials were used. The efficacy estimates were obtained from the study in Kenya and Uganda.⁷ This placebo-controlled trial used three courses of monthly PMC regimen with DP administered at the end of the 2nd (14 days post-discharge), 6th, and 10th weeks post-discharge. Each course comprised of three doses of DP given once daily. Adherence to the first dose of each monthly course was assessed during home visits as directly observed therapy. Daily telephone contact with caretakers and random home visits were used to verify the adherence to each course's second and third doses. Mortality and readmission rates were assessed for six months post-discharge.

The adherence data were obtained from the trial in Malawi that assessed adherence to the same PMC regimen and compared community-based with facility-based delivery strategies.⁸ Community-based PMC consisted of providing all three PMC courses to the caretakers at the time of hospital discharge combined with instructions on when and how to administer the PMC courses at home. Facility-based PMC consisted of instructions to the caretakers to collect each PMC treatment course from the hospital's outpatient department (OPD). After each course, adherence was determined by inspection of blister packs collected during unannounced home visits. Community-based PMC resulted in higher adherence than facility-based (71% vs 52% adherence to the full three courses). We categorised adherence into high (all nine tablets taken, three per course), medium (six to eight

tablets), low (three to five tablets), and very low or no adherence (zero to two tablets). We used these adherence rates to project the efficacy of PMC under programmatic conditions. (Figure S1)

All study hospitals in Malawi, Uganda (public hospitals) and Kenya (public and private hospitals) were located in high malaria transmission areas. Both trials included children younger than five years admitted for all-cause severe anaemia, excluding severe anaemia due to genetic factors (e.g. sickle cell disease), trauma, or malignancies. Hospitalised children received the standard of care for severe anaemia, including blood transfusions, parenteral antimalarials (in case of severe malarial anaemia) and antibiotics where indicated. At discharge, all children received the standard of care consisting of 3-day antimalarial treatment with oral artemether-lumefantrine (AL), which provides an average of about 13 days of post-treatment prophylaxis against malaria, regardless of the presence of malaria parasites.

DECISION MODELS

The cost-effectiveness of community-based and facility-based PMC were compared against the standard of care for Malawi, Kenya, and Uganda. We developed three novel Markov decision models using TreeAge Pro 2022 software, employing deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analyses. For each country, we combined data from the efficacy trial in Kenya and Uganda, the implementation trial in Malawi, data from interviews and process observations in Malawi, and data from the literature. The models used the three health states *healthy*, *severely sick*, and *dead*, with severe sickness defined as any hospital admission. The modelled cohort entered the model upon the first PMC course, 14 days (two weeks) after discharge from the hospital. We assumed the cohort to start in the *healthy* state and then move within the model in monthly cycles until six months were completed. At the end of each cycle, children in the cohort could change between the *healthy* and *severely sick* states. The terminal *dead* state could be reached from either the *healthy* or *severely sick* states. Non-severe health events, mostly clinic visits for uncomplicated clinical malaria, were modelled as occurring within a monthly cycle in the *healthy* state. We calculated incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICER) as the costs-per-quality-adjusted-life year (QALY) gained, comparing the three strategies for each country (Table 2).

EFFECTS AND REWARDS

Lacking quality of life weights, we used inverted annual disability weights from the 2019 Global Burden of Disease study for the severe and moderate sickness states to estimate QALYs. Within the first six months, completing a month in the healthy state was rewarded with the monthly equivalent of one full QALY. Any hospital readmission (*severely sick*) during this period incurred a reduction of the monthly equivalent of a full QALY by the average disability weight of the readmission causes in the efficacy trial (0.158 QALY). Based on the same data, any disutility from non-severe health events within the healthy state was equated to two weeks of the average disability weight of these events (0.046 QALY).⁹ Children that died within six months did not receive any reward for that or consecutive months. Based on our assumption of complete recovery by six months, surviving children were awarded their 2018 national average health-adjusted life expectancy subtracted by their average age at study completion (Malawi: 54.7 years; Kenya: 56.0 years; Uganda: 56.0 years).¹⁰ The rewards were not half-cycle-corrected because of the relatively short cycle length. We used 3% global discounting for all costs and utilities.

The monthly transitions between the three health states were controlled by transition probabilities extracted from the efficacy trial's health outcomes (*Table S2*).⁷ We assumed that PMC and placebo outcomes from the efficacy trial corresponded to the efficacy of 100% and 0% adherence to PMC, respectively. We further assumed a linear dose-response and matched the mean number of tablets administered per adherence category with the corresponding efficacy value. For example, *high adherence* (9 out of 9 tablets taken) corresponded to 100% of the observed efficacy, whereas in the *medium adherence* category the assumed PMC efficacy was 67%. In this example, the modelled probabilities of death or readmission for this adherence category were accordingly adjusted to combine 67% probabilities corresponding to the trial's PMC-arm with 33% of probabilities corresponding to the trial's placebo-arm. The same was done by linear interpolation for the other two adherence categories (*Figure S1*). We disregarded information about the order of courses adhered to (for example, we ignored whether the 1st, 2nd or 3rd course of PMC was skipped in a child that received six out of nine tablets) because no evidence existed how this impacted PMC efficacy.

COST DATA

We combined the healthcare provider perspective with the patients' household perspective to estimate the societal cost of PMC-implementation. We included both intervention-related costs and the costs of adverse health events during the discharge period. We employed a pragmatic ingredients approach, based on a mixed-methods inquiry, to determine costs that were incurred directly or indirectly related to the PMC intervention and due to health outcomes in children post-discharge.¹¹

We collected provider intervention cost data at Zomba Central Hospital in Malawi in 2018. For Kenya and Uganda, personnel salaries were based on local rates. We adopted providers' cost of DP from the national procurement systems (Malawi) and the literature (Kenya, Uganda), with an added 30% for handling and wastage (*Table S6*). Pharmacies' additional costs to disseminate and orient patients on PMC in Malawi, according to the two PMC strategies, were determined by time and motion observations and average salaries of the involved personnel (*Table S7*). The intervention costs to households, i.e. the cost of receiving and administering DP, were prospectively collected alongside both trials and then applied to the specific intervention arms, for example, by including the travel-related cost to collect the PMC courses in the facility-based strategy arm (*Table S8*).

Both delivery strategies of PMC started two weeks post discharge. The baseline cost for the standard of care incurred before starting the first post-discharge course of PMC and was therefore assumed to be 0 USD for all three arms. The intervention cost to the providers was estimated to be between 2.5 and 4.5 USD for both intervention arms in all countries. In contrast, the intervention costs to households differed substantially, both between the delivery arms and countries. Community-based delivery, i.e., receiving all three PMC courses upon discharge with instructions on how to administer them, was estimated to cost caretakers an average of 0.26 USD in Malawi, and 0.09 and 0.07 USD in Kenya and Uganda, respectively. Facility-based delivery resulted in substantially higher costs incurred by households (7.43 USD in Malawi and 10.09 and 10.16 USD in Kenya and Uganda) due to the additional travels to the hospital pharmacy required to collect monthly PMC courses. The households' costs to administer a PMC course were assumed to be the same in both arms. The households' lost productivity due to PMC was estimated as the value of time spent providing the care, including travel and time at the hospital. We valued the time using the minimum national salary rates of 2018. Direct and indirect costs were allowed to vary by country (*Table 1, S9*).

COST OF ADVERSE HEALTH EVENTS

We generally assumed the cost per hospital readmission after discharge to be the same in all arms and that they only differed by country (*Table 2*). As a proxy for the provider and household costs for any “all-cause” readmission, we used the average costs incurred during the treatment for severe anaemia at Zomba Central Hospital, Malawi. Patient and clinical pathways were recorded by following clinical practice and interviewing hospital staff. The costs of involved personnel were calculated based on hospitals’ average salaries for these positions and reported time spent per patient. Fifty random treatment records of children enrolled in the implementation trial in Malawi were reviewed for treatment duration, medication and procedures provided. The cost of medicines and equipment was itemised, valued, and costed based on Malawi’s central health equipment procurement database. Extra costs for handling and wastage was also added (*Table S5*).¹² These were adopted for Kenya and Uganda. We excluded all costs related to a child’s death, such as funeral costs.

Blood transfusion costs were estimated separately due to their significant share in the total costs. 70% of the blood available at Zomba Central hospital was obtained from the central blood bank and 30% from local donations.¹³ We used this ratio to estimate blood transfusion costs for Malawi. For Kenya and Uganda, we relied on WHO cost estimates and the literature.^{4,14} Approximately 42% of readmissions in the control arm of the efficacy trial required blood transfusions, compared to 29% in the intervention arm (*Table S6*). We estimated the average transfusions needed for the different adherence categories using linear interpolation.

Non-severe health events comprised outpatient visits at health centres and hospital outpatient departments. We established the average costs for a non-severe illness by employing the process as for the readmission cost. In the absence of access to patient files, we approximated average medication costs based on standard of care for the most frequent diagnosis: uncomplicated clinical malaria (85%).⁷ Support services costs including IT, laundry and cleaning were allocated using the annual share of malaria-related admissions among the paediatrics patients as allocation key; maintenance costs were allocated using the surface share of the paediatrics inpatient ward and outpatient department as allocation key (*Table S8*). Both costs were adopted for Kenya and Uganda. Hospital capital costs were disregarded as all relevant facilities in Malawi were publicly owned and over 30 years old.

Direct household costs and time used due to adverse health events were collected from caregivers of children partaking in the trials. We estimated indirect household costs as productive time lost for the emergency-related time, valued by minimum national salary rates (*Table S9*). All cost data collected during the trials were converted into USD, using the exchange rates of June 2018. All others were inflation adjusted to 2018.

ANALYSIS AND UNCERTAINTY

Univariate deterministic sensitivity analyses of key input variables were performed using +/- one standard deviation of their mean values. We used +/- 50% ranges for point estimates of costs, which typically have larger variation than other data, and +/-25% for other variables where we lacked inference data. We report one-way sensitivity analysis results as Tornado diagrams with pairwise comparisons of two strategies.

As explained above, we assumed a linear dose-effect relationship of DP in the base-case analysis, thus a proportionally reduced effect with lower adherence. We conducted scenario analyses for a concave and convex dose-effect curve leading to higher or lower efficacy for the medium and low adherence categories (S1). We performed a probabilistic sensitivity analysis for each country using Monte Carlo simulation with 10,000 iterations. For improved visibility, the corresponding graphs only show 150 iterations. Distribution shapes and confidence intervals determined the parameters of the analysis where they were available. In their absence, the ranges from the deterministic sensitivity analysis were adopted with standard distributions for costs (gamma) and probabilities (beta).

1 RESULTS

3.1 COST-EFFECTIVENESS

The mean expected cost of implementing community-based PMC per child treated in Malawi, Kenya, and Uganda was 22.91, 28.33, and 28.10 USD, respectively. The implementation costs were more than outweighed by saved costs for readmission compared to standard care, with a mean expected saving per child of 22.08, 45.24, and 23.35 USD when using community-based delivery (*Table 2*). The most important saving was reduced costs for blood transfusions (*Figure 2S*). With this strategy, health care providers' net cost saving per child receiving PMC was 19.12, 25.71, 19.74 USD, respectively (*Table 2*).

The mean expected effects are relatively less pronounced when taking a lifetime perspective. PMC primarily reduces readmissions, which was assumed to reduce a child's quality of life over one month. Differences in child mortality have a greater impact on average life expectancy. However, the difference in mortality between the strategies is less pronounced. Over a lifetime, the combination of reduced mortality and morbidity results in an average gain of 0.3 to 0.4 QALY per child treated using facility- or community-based delivery of PMC, compared to standard of care.

Both PMC strategies were cost-saving as they were less costly and more effective than standard of care over the lifetime of a child eligible for PMC. These results were largely driven by cost-savings from the much lower number of non-severe and severe adverse events in the PMC arms relative to the standard of care. In each country, community-based delivery was the most cost-effective strategy. The higher household costs in the facility-based delivery strategy to obtain PMC at the facilities and the associated lower adherence/efficacy compared to community-based PMC make this strategy sub-optimal for PMC delivery.

3.2 SENSITIVITY ANALYSES

One-way deterministic sensitivity analyses showed that the readmission and mortality probabilities were the most influential individual determinant of the ICERs for both strategies (*Figure 1*). No single parameters were sufficiently influential for facility-based PMC or standard of care to become the optimal strategy. Only unrealistically large changes to any other single parameters could thus lead to a conclusion-changing base-case ICER. Univariate sensitivity analysis of the Malawi data showed that community-based delivery was consistently more cost-effective than facility-based delivery (*Figure 1*). Deterministic sensitivity analysis showed similar results for Uganda and Kenya. Changing the linear dose-effect assumption to convex or concave scenarios did not change the ranking in any of the three countries.

The probabilistic sensitivity analysis using Monte Carlo simulations indicated that the differences between the strategies' ranking were largely driven by costs, shown in the horizontal layering of the strategies. Changes in effectiveness are less influential, shown by only small changes between strategy clusters related to the x-axis. (*Figure 2*).

Pairwise comparisons of strategies' incremental costs and effectiveness in Malawi were assessed against a willingness-to-pay (WTP) threshold set at one GDP per capita in 2017, i.e. 535 USD (*Figure 3*). These analyses show that the costs of community-based delivery of PMC were lower and more effective than the standard of care in 94% of the iterations (*Figure 3a*). The corresponding value for facility-based delivery was 92% (*Figure 3b*). When comparing the two PMC strategies, 78% of iterations showed a higher effect and lower costs for community-based PMC (*Figure 3c*). Similar findings were obtained for the models for Kenya and Uganda. In sum, results illustrate that community-based PMC has a high probability of being superior not only to standard care but also to facility-based PMC.

2 DISCUSSION

This cost-effectiveness analysis showed that both PMC strategies were cost-saving. They were less costly and more effective in terms of quality-adjusted life-years than the standard of care from a facility and household perspective in all three countries. The main driver of the dominance is the vastly reduced costs related to the reduced number of readmissions in the PMC arms relative to the standard of care. Community-delivered PMC was the most cost-saving of the two strategies because the repeated multiple hour-travels for drug collection in the facility-based strategy presented the caregivers with higher costs and, consequently, a disincentive to adhere. These results remained robust in the deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analysis and were consistent across all three countries. The results of our general efficacy estimates by adherence were also robust. We assumed a linear dose-response in the absence of real-life dose-response data. However, we adjusted for this uncertainty through scenario analyses and the probabilistic sensitivity of the models, neither of which resulted in changed cost-effectiveness rankings.

Establishing the cost-effectiveness of an intervention is essential for informed priority setting in a health system. We expect our results to be useful for policy considerations. One strength of our analysis is high internal validity for south-eastern Africa, combining context-specific efficacy estimates from a large placebo-controlled efficacy trial in Uganda and Kenya with strategy-specific adherence data from a delivery mechanism trial in Malawi. By adjusting PMC's proven efficacy with

robust adherence data, we offer a modelling method to tailor cost-effectiveness analyses for greater external validity and policy relevance more broadly.

Limitations include using facility costing data for Kenya and Uganda partly based on data obtained in Malawi. Although we used country-specific personnel and blood costs to control for the largest share of between country-differences, some directly adopted costs may result in inaccurate estimates. In addition, we built our model with the PMC trial design in mind rather than large-scale implementation. For example, the current standard of care consists of AL administered to children as soon as they can take oral medication. However, if PMC, when implemented, would consist of four courses of DP, with the first course started while the child is still in hospital, this would replace the standard of care. PMC implementation, in that case, would replace, rather than extend, the standard of care. However, we see no reason to expect less robust results under this strategy. Lastly, we ignored programming costs. Our analysis does not consider the costs of implementing this new PMC strategy, which, unlike intermittent preventive treatment in infants, does not have an existing platform through which PMC can be delivered.

CONCLUSION

PMC has a very high probability of being cost-saving. It is less costly and more effective in increasing health-adjusted life expectancy than the current standard of care in Kenya, Uganda, and Malawi. The key driver for this result is that PMC is a relatively cheap and simple intervention with a high potential to reduce costly hospital readmissions and death. In addition, provision of all PMC courses to the caretaker at discharge, combined with instructions on administering them, is less costly for providers and households and more effective than facility-based delivery that requires the caretaker to collect each monthly dose of PMC.

ARTICLE INFORMATION

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

MJK, BR: Methodology, Data curation, Software, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft, Visualisation, Writing - Review & Editing. BR: Methodology, Data Validation Software, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft, Visualisation, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. KP: Data validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing, Project Administration. FTK: Conceptualisation, Data validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. TNG, AD, TK, AM, RO, CJ, RI: Data curation, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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TABLES

Table 1: Composite costs for PMC implementation models per country

PERSPECTIVE: Cost input Country	Base Case			Range (CI; point estimates: +/- 50%)				Distribution	Source
	Standard of care (base case)	PMC Community Delivery	PMC Facility Delivery	low		high			
				Community Delivery	Facility Delivery	Community Delivery	Facility Delivery		
Intervention Cost									
PROVIDER: Dihydroartemisinin–piperazine (DHP) price per treatment, \$									
Kenya	0.00	2.97	2.97	1.48		4.45		point estimate (normal)	MSH International Medical Products Price Guide (2015)
Malawi	0.00	2.36	2.36	1.18		3.54		point estimate (normal)	Fernandez (2019) international prices
Uganda	0.00	2.30	2.30	1.15		3.45		point estimate (normal)	Global Fund Price Reference Report (2015) for Uganda
PROVIDER: Pharmacist time cost, \$									time estimates by pharmacist; official salaries
Kenya	0.00	0.72	1.44	0.36	0.72	1.08	2.16	point estimate (normal)	
Malawi	0.00	0.12	0.24	0.06	0.12	0.18	0.36	point estimate (normal)	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda	0.00	0.29	0.58	0.15	0.29	0.435	0.87	point estimate (normal)	
PATIENT: Total Household drug collection cost, \$									
Kenya	0.00	0.09	10.09	0.05	5.05	0.135	15.135	Gamma	
Malawi	0.00	0.26	7.43	0.13	3.72	0.39	11.145	Gamma	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda	0.00	0.07	10.16	0.04	5.08	0.105	15.24	Gamma	

PATIENT: total household drug administration cost, \$						
Kenya	0.00	1.94	5.03	6.34	Gamma	trial data Kwambai 2020
Malawi	0.00	1.07	0.09	0.38	Gamma	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda	0.00	3.31	7.56	9.31	Gamma	trial data Kwambai 2020
Costs of adverse health events						
PROVIDER: total health personnel cost per inpatient treatment, \$						
Kenya		15.74	7.87	23.61	Point estimate	
Malawi		10.56	5.28	15.84	Point estimate	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda		11.45	5.73	17.18	Point estimate	
PROVIDER: cost per blood transfusion per inpatient treatment incl. laboratory costs, transportation and wastage, \$						
Kenya		78.00	39.00	117.00	Point estimate	
Malawi		82.41	41.21	123.62	Point estimate	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished) combined with adjusted costs from Medina-Lara (2012)
Uganda		65.00	32.50	97.50	Point estimate	
PROVIDER: sum of medicines, equipment and other material costs per inpatient treatment, including SOC at discharge, \$						
Kenya		18.67	9.34	28.01	Point estimate	
Malawi		18.67	9.34	28.01	Point estimate	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda		18.67	9.34	28.01	Point estimate	

PROVIDER: sum of hospital administration and support services per inpatient treatment, \$					
Kenya	12.37	6.19	18.56	Point estimate	
Malawi	3.04	1.52	4.56	Point estimate	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda	5.17	2.59	7.76	Point estimate	
PROVIDER: total cost per outpatient treatment, \$					
Kenya	3.39	1.77	5.01	Point estimate	
Malawi	2.40	1.22	3.58	Point estimate	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda	2.53	1.31	3.75	Point estimate	
PATIENT: total cost per inpatient stay incl. transport and lost productivity, and patient transfusion cost (only applicable for Kenya), \$					
Kenya	55.26	35.09	55.43	Gamma	trial data Kwambai 2020
Malawi	12.94	11.35	14.54	Gamma	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda	20.04	18.10	21.98	Gamma	trial data Kwambai 2020
PATIENT: total household cost per outpatient visit incl. transport and lost productivity, \$					
Kenya	11.92	9.34	14.49	Gamma	trial data Kwambai 2020
Malawi	5.34	4.31	6.70	Gamma	PMC Malawi cost study (unpublished)
Uganda	9.60	8.45	10.75	Gamma	trial data Kwambai 2020

Table 2: Incremental cost-effectiveness rankings per country. When comparing the three strategies, PMC Community distribution is the absolutely dominant strategy: it is at the same time least costly over the expected lifetime of a child (lowest cost per QALY gained) and yielded the most health-adjusted life-years. The incremental quality-adjusted life years (QALY) specify each strategy's average impact on mortality and morbidity. The incremental values indicate that facility distribution also absolutely dominates the standard of care. However, it is less cost-saving and less effective than community-based distribution when compared to standard of care.

Country	Strategy	Cost (USD)				Effectiveness (QALY)		Cost-Effectiveness Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio
		Health care provider cost	Household cost	Total cost	Incremental cost (total)	Health-adjusted life expectancy	Incremental QALY	
Malawi	Standard of Care	36.34	8.71	44.99		52.6839		negative
	PMC Facility-delivered	19.79	11.47	31.22	-13.77	52.9993	0.3154	negative
	PMC Community-delivered	17.22	5.73	22.91	-8.30	53.0496	0.0503	dominant
Kenya	Standard of Care	44.35	29.44	73.58		53.8580		negative
	PMC Facility-delivered	22.71	19.59	42.21	-31.37	54.1911	0.3331	negative
	PMC Community-delivered	18.63	10.05	28.33	-13.87	54.2450	0.0539	dominant
Uganda	Standard of Care	37.42	14.14	51.46		53.8617		negative
	PMC Facility-delivered	20.46	18.58	38.98	-12.48	54.1941	0.3324	negative
	PMC Community-delivered	17.68	10.48	28.10	-10.87	54.2474	0.0532	dominant

FIGURES

Figure 1: Univariate (one-way) sensitivity analyses summarised as Tornado diagrams for the two delivery strategies, each compared with standard of care in Malawi, and a comparison among them. The variables are sorted according to decreasing sensitivity on the ICER. The ICER is expressed in terms of USD per QALY gained.

Figure 2: Monte Carlo Simulation of 150 iterations per strategy for Malawi, Kenya, and Uganda

Figure 3: Simulation results of incremental Cost Effectiveness Scatterplots for PMC in Malawi with pairwise comparisons of the three strategies, with willingness to pay-line of 1 GDP per capita: a) Community-based delivery of PMC vs. Standard of care; b) Facility-delivered PMC vs. Standard of care; Community- vs. Facility-based delivery of PMC

Table S6: Medication overview used for SA treatment in Malawi, derived from a sample of 50 children.

Medication for in-patient treatment	Unit price (MKW)	Units needed per child if indicated	Cost if indicated (MKW)	Costs with additional wastage and freight (30%)	Proportion of children with indication	Average total per SA treatment (MKW)	USD
Medication SA treatment							
Albendazole – 6418/1000	6.42	2.00	12.84	16.98	0.30	5.09	0.01
Amoxycillin 125mg/5ml suspension, PFR to make 100ml	676.40	1.00	676.40	894.54	0.05	44.73	0.06
Artesunate 60mg PFR, with diluent	1472.00	3.00	4416.00	5840.16	1.03	5986.16	8.20
Benzylpenicillin 3g (5MU), PFR	149.00	13.00	1937.00	2561.68	0.48	1216.80	1.67
Ceftriaxone 1g, PFR	178.00	5.00	890.00	1177.03	0.13	153.01	0.21
Dextrose 50%, 50ml	457.00	1.00	457.00	604.38	0.08	48.35	0.07
Diazepam 5mg/ml, 2ml	121.00	1.00	121.00	160.02	0.03	4.00	0.01
Furosemide (Frusemide) 10mg/ml, 2ml	40.00	1.00	40.00	52.90	0.05	2.65	0.00
Gentamycin Sulphate 40mg/ml, 2ml	43.00	5.00	215.00	284.34	0.33	92.41	0.13
Ferrous sulphate 200mg / folic acid 250 micrograms, coated tablets	2.25	30.00	67.56	89.35	0.08	6.70	0.01
LA: 22656/(24*30)	37.76	6.00	226.56	299.63	0.53	157.30	0.22
Nystatin oral suspension 100,000 IU/ml, 20ml	399.00	1.00	399.00	527.68	0.13	65.96	0.09
Paracetamol syrup 120mg/5ml, 100ml	313.00	9.00	2817.00	3725.48	0.85	3166.66	4.34
Phenobarbitone sodium 200mg/ml, 1ml	637.00	1.00	637.00	842.43	0.03	21.06	0.03
Zinc sulphate 20mg, Tablets	4.50	10.00	45.00	59.51	0.03	1.49	0.00
Average medication cost for SA treatment per child						10972.37	15.03
Medication at discharge							
Albendazole – 6418/1000	6.42	2.00	12.84	16.98	0.70	11.88	0.02
LA: 22656/(24*30)	37.76	6.00	226.56	299.63	0.48	142.32	0.19
Ferrous sulphate 200mg / folic acid 250 micrograms, coated tablets	2.25	30.00	67.56	89.35	0.93	82.65	0.11
Average medication cost for SA treatment per child						236.85	0.32

Table S7: Facility personnel costs for intervention, readmission and non-severe treatment, based on hospital practice in Malawi

			Malawi		Kenya		Uganda	
Hospital employee position		average time spent per child based on observations in Zomba Central Hosp., Malawi (hour)	hourly personnel cost (USD)	personnel cost per child treated with PMC	hourly personnel cost (USD)	personnel cost per child treated with PMC	hourly personnel cost (USD)	personnel cost per child treated with PMC
PMC Intervention	Pharmacist Community PMC	0.08	1.43	0.12	5.75	0.48	4.61	0.38
	Pharmacist Facility PMC	0.17	1.43	0.24	5.75	0.96	4.61	0.77
Readmission	Clinician	0.87	3.25	2.81	7.10	6.15	6.60	5.72
	Nurse	1.83	2.85	5.23	3.46	6.34	1.46	2.67
	Pharmacist	0.17	1.43	0.24	5.75	0.96	4.61	0.77
	patient attendant	0.42	0.97	0.41	2.43	1.01	0.02	0.01
	clerk	0.18	1.03	0.19	2.57	0.47	1.54	0.28
	average personnel cost per child treated			8.87		14.94		9.46
clinic/OPD	Clinician	0.08	3.25	0.27	7.10	0.59	6.60	0.55
	Nurse	0.33	2.85	0.95	3.46	1.15	1.46	0.49
	Pharmacist	0.08	1.43	0.12	5.75	0.48	4.61	0.38
	patient attendant	0.08	0.97	0.08	2.43	0.20	0.02	0.00
	clerk	0.17	1.03	0.17	2.57	0.43	1.54	0.26
	average personnel cost per child treated			1.59		2.85		1.68

Table S8: Support service costs based on annual expenses of Zomba Central Hospital, Malawi

Facility running cost and support services	Total expenses 2017-18	proportion of the pediatric ward (IPD) in the entire hospital	proportion of outpatient pediatric department (OPD) in the entire hospital	estimated annual cost, IPD	estimated annual cost, OPD	per patient cost (28735 patients/yr)	Average SA treatment in malawi: 4.66 days	per patient cost (14367 patients/yr)
Medical equipment	5000000.00	0.18	0.04	900000.00	180000.00	31.32	145.95	12.53
Building rehabilitation	5500000.00	0.18	0.04	990000.00	198000.00	34.45	160.55	13.78
Maintenance	12000000.00	0.18	0.04	2160000.00	432000.00	75.17	350.29	30.07
Internet	7200000.00	0.18	0.04	1296000.00	259200.00	45.10	210.17	18.04
Water	43000000.00	0.18	0.04	7740000.00	1548000.00	269.36	1255.21	107.75
Landscaping	12000000.00	0.18	0.04	2160000.00	432000.00	75.17	350.29	30.07
Security service	15000000.00	0.18	0.04	2700000.00	540000.00	93.96	437.86	37.59
Total cost per patient (MKW)						624.53	2910.33	124.91
Total cost per patient, Malawi (USD)						0.86	3.99	0.17
Total cost per patient, Kenya (average inpatient duration: 5.54 days) (USD)							4.74	0.20
Total cost per patient, Uganda (average inpatient duration: 3.86 days) (USD)							3.30	0.14

Table S9: Household costs for intervention, readmission and non-severe treatment

Household Cost: PMC Intervention									
	Uganda			Kenya			Malawi		
	<i>mean</i>	<i>CI</i>		<i>mean</i>	<i>CI</i>		<i>mean</i>	<i>CI</i>	
		<i>lower</i>	<i>upper</i>		<i>lower</i>	<i>upper</i>		<i>lower</i>	<i>upper</i>
financial cost due to administering PMC at home (UGX, KES,MKW)	10820.48	8516.66	13124.29	6.46	1.24	11.68	94.26	41.21	147.31
time spent administering full treatment, 9 tablets (Minutes)	138.70	127.69	127.69	178.57	159.42	197.72	258.00	85.36	430.64
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	1414.21	1301.89	1301.89	190.09	169.70	210.47	680.92	225.29	1136.54
total cost intervention (UGX, KES,MKW)	12234.69	9818.56	14426.19	196.55	170.94	222.15	775.18	266.50	1283.86
USD	3.31	2.65	3.90	1.94	1.68	2.19	1.07	0.37	1.78
Cost of DHP collection at hospital pharmacy per course (facility-based delivery)									
money spent on transport (UGX, KES,MKW)	16146.13	15564.72	16727.53	362.30	332.31	392.29	1818.06	1557.95	2078.18
duration of transportation and hospital visit (hours)	4.20	4.04	4.36	2.22	2.11	2.32	5.34	4.94	5.75
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	21841.49	21027.12	22655.86	1203.72	1147.04	1260.40	7193.85	6650.37	7737.34
total costs for clinic visit	37987.62	36591.84	39383.39	1566.02	1479.35	1652.69	9011.92	8208.32	9815.51
USD	10.27	9.89	10.64	15.43	14.57	16.28	12.46	11.35	13.58
Household costs: Hospital readmission									
	Uganda			Kenya			Malawi		
	<i>mean</i>	<i>CI</i>		<i>mean</i>	<i>CI</i>		<i>mean</i>	<i>CI</i>	
		<i>lower</i>	<i>upper</i>		<i>lower</i>	<i>upper</i>		<i>lower</i>	<i>upper</i>
time spent in the hospital (days)	5.80	5.31	6.29	6.32	4.86	7.78	5.05	4.64	5.46
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	30162.35	27636.81	32683.80	3430.97	2638.34	4223.59	6803.34	6251.38	7355.29

money spent at the hospital (UGX, KES,MKW)	24381.88	21204.01	27559.74	446.54	223.27	669.81	99.32	37.94	160.71
money spent on transport (UGX, KES,MKW)	15947.08	14752.78	17141.37	602.50	384.37	820.63	1818.06	1557.95	2078.18
total costs of readmission	70491.31	63593.60	77384.91	4480.01	3245.98	5714.03	8720.73	7847.28	9594.18
USD	19.05	17.19	20.91	44.14	31.98	56.30	12.06	10.85	13.27

Household costs: Outpatient department or clinic visit for non-severe event									
	Uganda			Kenya			Malawi		
	mean	CI		mean	CI		mean	CI	
		lower	upper		lower	upper		lower	upper
time spent by caregiver and partner for caring at home, transport to the clinic, time at the clinic (hours)	29.42	27.17	31.68	26.63	24.42	28.84	26.48	22.51	30.46
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	8516.94	7136.45	9896.06	710.89	569.53	851.88	1739.10	1346.00	2368.25
money spent at the hospital (UGX, KES,MKW)	7149.06	4982.98	9315.13	98.21	49.11	147.32	21.31	8.14	34.49
money spent on transport (UGX, KES,MKW)	19859.74	15564.72	16727.53	362.30	332.31	392.29	1818.06	1557.95	2078.18
total costs of clinic visit	35525.73	27684.15	35938.73	1171.40	950.94	1391.48	3578.47	2912.09	4480.91
USD	9.60	7.48	9.71	11.54	9.37	13.71	4.95	4.03	6.20

SUPPLEMENT TO: KÜHL ET AL., COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF POST-DISCHARGE MALARIA CHEMOPREVENTION AMONG PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH SEVERE ANAEMIA IN MALAWI, KENYA, AND UGANDA

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Figure S1: Dose effect (DE) estimates of PMC by adherence category, including scenario analyses +/- 20% for a convex and a concave dose-effect curve between no and full adherence.

Figure S2: Overview of decision model, with a decision tree to control adherence and a Markov model to control health outcomes over the follow-up period of 6 months

SUPPLEMENTAL TABLES

Table S3: Transition probabilities for standard of care arm and relative risk for transitions with PMC (derived from Kwambai et al, 2020)

Trial arm allocation	Relative risk of health states with PMC			
	starting state	transition state		
		healthy	severely sick	dead
Transition probability for standard of care (base case)	healthy	0.8710	0.1238	0.0051
Relative risk for transition with PMC (full adherence)		1.0954	0.3391	0.7490
Transition probability for standard of care (base case)	severely sick	0.9043	0.0891	0.0066
Relative risk for transition with PMC (full adherence)		1.0121	0.8738	1.0472
Probability standard of care arm	dead	-	-	1
Probability PMC arm		-	-	1

Table S4: The five arms used in the implementation trial (Gondwe, 2022) were pooled in two arms: community and facility-based delivery

Category of adherence	Community-based delivery of PMC				Facility-based delivery of PMC				
	3 arms in Gondwe (2021)				2 arms in Gondwe (2021)				
	Com-SMS	Com+SMS	Com+HSA	Total	Community-based PMC (%)	Fac-SMS	Fac+SMS	Total	Facility-based PMC (%)
No or very low	1	2	2	5	2.3	4	2	6	4.0
Low	8	4	6	18	8.1	12	14	26	17.3
Medium	16	9	17	42	19.0	21	19	40	26.7
High	43	59	54	156	70.6	39	39	78	52.0
Total	68 (100)	74 (100)	79 (100)	221	100.0	76 (100)	74 (100)	150.0	100.0

Table S5: Medication and medical equipment costs for intervention, readmission and non-severe treatment

Medication and medical equipment		average amount needed for standard treatment, based on Malawi data (unit)	Malawi				Kenya				Uganda			
			cost per unit	mean cost per child (USD)	lower	upper limit	cost per unit	mean cost per child (USD)	lower	upper limit	cost per unit	mean cost per child (USD)	lower	upper limit
PMC Intervention	dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine	9	0.33	2.97	1.48	4.45	0.25	2.25	1.13	3.38	0.26	2.30	1.15	3.45
	average sum medication for SA treatment : see Table S6	n/a; see Table S6	n/a	15.03	7.52	22.55	see Malawi				see Malawi			
Readmission	blood transfusion, placebo-arm , efficacy trial (Kwambai 2020))	0.42	65.93	27.69	13.85	41.54	73.10	30.70	15.35	46.05	82.40	34.61	17.72	51.91
	blood transfusion, PMC-arm , efficacy trial (Kwambai 2020))	0.29	65.93	19.38	9.69	29.08	73.10	21.49	10.75	32.24	82.40	24.23	12.41	36.34
Clinic/OPD	standard of care medication, clinical malaria: artemether/lumefanterine	6	0.14	0.85	0.43	1.28	see Malawi				see Malawi			

Table S6: Medication overview used for SA treatment in Malawi, derived from a sample of 50 children.

Medication for in-patient treatment	Unit price (MKW)	Units needed per child if indicated	Cost if indicated (MKW)	Costs with additional wastage and freight (30%)	Proportion of children with indication	Average total per SA treatment (MKW)	USD
Medication SA treatment							
Albendazole – 6418/1000	6.42	2.00	12.84	16.98	0.30	5.09	0.01
Amoxycillin 125mg/5ml suspension, PFR to make 100ml	676.40	1.00	676.40	894.54	0.05	44.73	0.06
Artesunate 60mg PFR, with diluent	1472.00	3.00	4416.00	5840.16	1.03	5986.16	8.20
Benzylpenicillin 3g (5MU), PFR	149.00	13.00	1937.00	2561.68	0.48	1216.80	1.67
Ceftriaxone 1g, PFR	178.00	5.00	890.00	1177.03	0.13	153.01	0.21
Dextrose 50%, 50ml	457.00	1.00	457.00	604.38	0.08	48.35	0.07
Diazepam 5mg/ml, 2ml	121.00	1.00	121.00	160.02	0.03	4.00	0.01
Furosemide (Frusemide) 10mg/ml, 2ml	40.00	1.00	40.00	52.90	0.05	2.65	0.00
Gentamycin Sulphate 40mg/ml, 2ml	43.00	5.00	215.00	284.34	0.33	92.41	0.13
Ferrous sulphate 200mg / folic acid 250 micrograms, coated tablets	2.25	30.00	67.56	89.35	0.08	6.70	0.01
LA: 22656/(24*30)	37.76	6.00	226.56	299.63	0.53	157.30	0.22
Nystatin oral suspension 100,000 IU/ml, 20ml	399.00	1.00	399.00	527.68	0.13	65.96	0.09
Paracetamol syrup 120mg/5ml, 100ml	313.00	9.00	2817.00	3725.48	0.85	3166.66	4.34
Phenobarbitone sodium 200mg/ml, 1ml	637.00	1.00	637.00	842.43	0.03	21.06	0.03
Zinc sulphate 20mg, Tablets	4.50	10.00	45.00	59.51	0.03	1.49	0.00
Average medication cost for SA treatment per child						10972.37	15.03
Medication at discharge							
Albendazole – 6418/1000	6.42	2.00	12.84	16.98	0.70	11.88	0.02
LA: 22656/(24*30)	37.76	6.00	226.56	299.63	0.48	142.32	0.19
Ferrous sulphate 200mg / folic acid 250 micrograms, coated tablets	2.25	30.00	67.56	89.35	0.93	82.65	0.11
Average medication cost for SA treatment per child						236.85	0.32

Table S7: Facility personnel costs for intervention, readmission and non-severe treatment, based on hospital practice in Malawi

			Malawi		Kenya		Uganda	
Hospital employee position		average time spent per child based on observations in Zomba Central Hosp., Malawi (hour)	hourly personnel cost (USD)	personnel cost per child treated with PMC	hourly personnel cost (USD)	personnel cost per child treated with PMC	hourly personnel cost (USD)	personnel cost per child treated with PMC
PMC Intervention	Pharmacist Community PMC	0.08	1.43	0.12	5.75	0.48	4.61	0.38
	Pharmacist Facility PMC	0.17	1.43	0.24	5.75	0.96	4.61	0.77
Readmission	Clinician	0.87	3.25	2.81	7.10	6.15	6.60	5.72
	Nurse	1.83	2.85	5.23	3.46	6.34	1.46	2.67
	Pharmacist	0.17	1.43	0.24	5.75	0.96	4.61	0.77
	patient attendant	0.42	0.97	0.41	2.43	1.01	0.02	0.01
	clerk	0.18	1.03	0.19	2.57	0.47	1.54	0.28
	average personnel cost per child treated			8.87		14.94		9.46
clinic/OPD	Clinician	0.08	3.25	0.27	7.10	0.59	6.60	0.55
	Nurse	0.33	2.85	0.95	3.46	1.15	1.46	0.49
	Pharmacist	0.08	1.43	0.12	5.75	0.48	4.61	0.38
	patient attendant	0.08	0.97	0.08	2.43	0.20	0.02	0.00
	clerk	0.17	1.03	0.17	2.57	0.43	1.54	0.26
	average personnel cost per child treated			1.59		2.85		1.68

Table S8: Support service costs based on annual expenses of Zomba Central Hospital, Malawi

Facility running cost and support services	Total expenses 2017-18	proportion of the pediatric ward (IPD) in the entire hospital	proportion of outpatient pediatric department (OPD) in the entire hospital	estimated annual cost, IPD	estimated annual cost, OPD	per patient cost (28735 patients/yr)	Average SA treatment in malawi: 4.66 days	per patient cost (14367 patients/yr)
Medical equipment	5000000.00	0.18	0.04	900000.00	180000.00	31.32	145.95	12.53
Building rehabilitation	5500000.00	0.18	0.04	990000.00	198000.00	34.45	160.55	13.78
Maintenance	12000000.00	0.18	0.04	2160000.00	432000.00	75.17	350.29	30.07
Internet	7200000.00	0.18	0.04	1296000.00	259200.00	45.10	210.17	18.04
Water	43000000.00	0.18	0.04	7740000.00	1548000.00	269.36	1255.21	107.75
Landscaping	12000000.00	0.18	0.04	2160000.00	432000.00	75.17	350.29	30.07
Security service	15000000.00	0.18	0.04	2700000.00	540000.00	93.96	437.86	37.59
Total cost per patient (MKW)						624.53	2910.33	124.91
Total cost per patient, Malawi (USD)						0.86	3.99	0.17
Total cost per patient, Kenya (average inpatient duration: 5.54 days) (USD)							4.74	0.20
Total cost per patient, Uganda (average inpatient duration: 3.86 days) (USD)							3.30	0.14

Table S9: Household costs for intervention, readmission and non-severe treatment

Household Cost: PMC Intervention									
	Uganda			Kenya			Malawi		
	mean	CI		mean	CI		mean	CI	
		lower	upper		lower	upper		lower	upper
financial cost due to administering PMC at home (UGX, KES,MKW)	10820.48	8516.66	13124.29	6.46	1.24	11.68	94.26	41.21	147.31
time spent administering full treatment, 9 tablets (Minutes)	138.70	127.69	127.69	178.57	159.42	197.72	258.00	85.36	430.64
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	1414.21	1301.89	1301.89	190.09	169.70	210.47	680.92	225.29	1136.54
total cost intervention (UGX, KES,MKW)	12234.69	9818.56	14426.19	196.55	170.94	222.15	775.18	266.50	1283.86
USD	3.31	2.65	3.90	1.94	1.68	2.19	1.07	0.37	1.78
Cost of DHP collection at hospital pharmacy per course (facility-based delivery)									
money spent on transport (UGX, KES,MKW)	16146.13	15564.72	16727.53	362.30	332.31	392.29	1818.06	1557.95	2078.18
duration of transportation and hospital visit (hours)	4.20	4.04	4.36	2.22	2.11	2.32	5.34	4.94	5.75
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	21841.49	21027.12	22655.86	1203.72	1147.04	1260.40	7193.85	6650.37	7737.34
total costs for clinic visit	37987.62	36591.84	39383.39	1566.02	1479.35	1652.69	9011.92	8208.32	9815.51
USD	10.27	9.89	10.64	15.43	14.57	16.28	12.46	11.35	13.58
Household costs: Hospital readmission									
	Uganda			Kenya			Malawi		
	mean	CI		mean	CI		mean	CI	
		lower	upper		lower	upper		lower	upper
time spent in the hospital (days)	5.80	5.31	6.29	6.32	4.86	7.78	5.05	4.64	5.46
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	30162.35	27636.81	32683.80	3430.97	2638.34	4223.59	6803.34	6251.38	7355.29

money spent at the hospital (UGX, KES,MKW)	24381.88	21204.01	27559.74	446.54	223.27	669.81	99.32	37.94	160.71
money spent on transport (UGX, KES,MKW)	15947.08	14752.78	17141.37	602.50	384.37	820.63	1818.06	1557.95	2078.18
total costs of readmission	70491.31	63593.60	77384.91	4480.01	3245.98	5714.03	8720.73	7847.28	9594.18
USD	19.05	17.19	20.91	44.14	31.98	56.30	12.06	10.85	13.27

Household costs: Outpatient department or clinic visit for non-severe event									
	Uganda			Kenya			Malawi		
	mean	CI		mean	CI		mean	CI	
		lower	upper		lower	upper		lower	upper
time spent by caregiver and partner for caring at home, transport to the clinic, time at the clinic (hours)	29.42	27.17	31.68	26.63	24.42	28.84	26.48	22.51	30.46
<i>equivalent min. salary, 8.5 hrs/day (UGX, KES,MKW)</i>	8516.94	7136.45	9896.06	710.89	569.53	851.88	1739.10	1346.00	2368.25
money spent at the hospital (UGX, KES,MKW)	7149.06	4982.98	9315.13	98.21	49.11	147.32	21.31	8.14	34.49
money spent on transport (UGX, KES,MKW)	19859.74	15564.72	16727.53	362.30	332.31	392.29	1818.06	1557.95	2078.18
total costs of clinic visit	35525.73	27684.15	35938.73	1171.40	950.94	1391.48	3578.47	2912.09	4480.91
USD	9.60	7.48	9.71	11.54	9.37	13.71	4.95	4.03	6.20